

A Solution to an Analysis Problem(1)

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1 Problem1

Let n be a positive integer, and let a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n be non-negative real numbers satisfying $a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_n = n$. Let b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n be a permutation of $a_1 + 1, a_2 + 1, \dots, a_n + 1$. Prove that there exists a positive integer i with $1 \leq i \leq n$ such that $a_i b_i \geq 2$.

2 Solution of Problem 1

By symmetry, we may assume without loss of generality that $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq \dots \geq a_n$. Notice that $\sum_{i=1}^n (a_i + a_{n+1-i}) = 2 \sum_{i=1}^n a_i = 2n$, so by the average value principle, there exists $1 \leq i \leq n$ such that $a_i + a_{n+1-i} \geq 2$. By symmetry, we may assume $i \leq \frac{n}{2}$ without loss of generality.

By the pigeonhole principle, there must exist $1 \leq j \leq n+1-i$ and $1 \leq k \leq i$ such that $b_k = a_j + 1$. Since $a_k \geq a_i$ and $b_k = a_j + 1 \geq a_{n+1-i} + 1$, we have $a_k + b_k \geq a_i + a_{n+1-i} + 1 \geq 3$. Moreover, since $i \leq \frac{n}{2}$, we know $a_i \geq a_{n+1-i}$, so $a_k \geq a_i \geq 1$. Thus, as $a_k \geq 1$ and $b_k \geq 1$, we have $(a_k - 1)(b_k - 1) \geq 0$, which implies $a_k b_k \geq a_k + b_k - 1$. From $a_k + b_k \geq 3$, it follows that $a_k b_k \geq 2$.

3 Problem 2

Let n be a positive integer. Let $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq \dots \geq a_n \geq 0$ satisfy $\sum_{i=1}^n a_i = n$. Denote $A = \{f \mid f \text{ is a bijection from } [n] \text{ to } [n]\}$ (where $[n] = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$). Define $b_{f(i)} = a_i + 1$. Suppose there exists $f \in A$ such that for all $i \in [n]$, $a_i b_i \leq 2$. Find the vector $\vec{a} = (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n)$ and the corresponding bijection f .

4 Solution of Problem 2

Suppose there exists $i \in [n]$ such that $a_i + a_{n+1-i} > 2$. Without loss of generality, assume $i \leq \frac{n+1}{2}$. On this basis, assume that for all $1 \leq j \leq n+1-i$, $f(j) \geq i+1$. Since the number of y_1 satisfying $1 \leq y_1 \leq n+1-i$ is $n+1-i$, and the number of y_2 satisfying $i+1 \leq y_2 \leq n$ is $n-i$, with $n+1-i > n-i$, this contradicts the fact that f is a bijection. Therefore, there exists $1 \leq j \leq n+1-i$ such that $1 \leq f(j) \leq i$. Since $j \leq n+1-i$, we have $a_j \geq a_{n+1-i}$. Since $1 \leq f(j) \leq i$, we have $a_{f(j)} \geq a_i$. Thus, $a_{f(j)} + b_{f(j)} = a_{f(j)} + a_j + 1 \geq a_{n+1-i} + a_i + 1 > 3$. Since $i \leq \frac{n+1}{2}$, we get $i \leq n+1-i$. Because the sequence $\{a_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq n}$ is non-increasing, it follows that $2a_i \geq a_i + a_{n+1-i} > 2$, so $a_i > 1$. Since $f(j) \leq i$, we have $a_{f(j)} \geq a_i > 1$. Since $b_{f(j)} = a_j + 1 \geq 1$, we obtain $(a_{f(j)} - 1)(b_{f(j)} - 1) \geq 0$. Thus, $a_{f(j)} b_{f(j)} \geq a_{f(j)} + b_{f(j)} - 1 > 3 - 1 = 2$, which is a contradiction. Therefore, for all $i \in [n]$ (where $[n]$ denotes $\{1, 2, \dots, n\}$), we have $a_i + a_{n+1-i} \leq 2$. Note that $2n = \sum_{i=1}^n (a_i + a_{n+1-i}) \leq \sum_{i=1}^n 2 = 2n$. Equality holds if and only if $a_i + a_{n+1-i} = 2$ for each i . Since equality holds for all terms, we conclude that for all $i \in [n]$, $a_i + a_{n+1-i} = 2$. Suppose there exists $i \in [n]$ such that $a_i \notin \{0, 1, 2\}$, and let j be the smallest such i . Suppose $j \geq \lfloor \frac{n+1}{2} \rfloor + 1$. Then, by the definition of j , for all $t \leq \lfloor \frac{n+1}{2} \rfloor$, we have $a_t \in \{0, 1, 2\}$. Since $a_{n+1-t} = 2 - a_t$, it follows that for all $t \geq \lceil \frac{n+1}{2} \rceil$, $a_t \in \{0, 1, 2\}$. Thus, for all $t \in [n]$, $a_t \in \{0, 1, 2\}$, which contradicts the assumption. Therefore, $j \leq \lfloor \frac{n+1}{2} \rfloor$.

Thus, $j \leq n+1-j$, so $a_j \geq a_{n+1-j}$. Then, $2a_j \geq a_j + a_{n+1-j} = 2$, hence $a_j \geq 1$. Since $a_j \notin \{0, 1, 2\}$, we have $a_j \in (1, 2)$. If $j = 1$, then $a_j b_j = a_1 b_1 = a_1 (a_{f^{-1}(1)} + 1) \geq a_1 (a_n + 1) = a_1 (3 - a_1) > 2$, which is a contradiction.

If $j \geq 2$ (with $n \geq 3$), then for all $1 \leq k \leq j-1$, we have $a_k = 2$. By $a_{n+1-k} = 2 - a_k$, it follows that for all $n+2-j \leq k \leq n$, $a_k = 0$. Since $a_j \in (0, 2)$, we have $a_{n+1-j} \in (0, 2)$. Because the sequence $\{a_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq n}$ is non-increasing, for all $j \leq k \leq n+1-j$, we have $a_k \in (0, 2)$.

Since for all $1 \leq k \leq j-1$, $2b_k = a_k b_k \leq 2$, we get $a_{f^{-1}(k)} + 1 = b_k \leq 1$, hence $a_{f^{-1}(k)} = 0$. Thus, for all $1 \leq k \leq j-1$, $n+2-j \leq f^{-1}(k) \leq n$. Therefore, $f^{-1}(j) \leq n+1-j$, so $a_{f^{-1}(j)} \geq a_{n+1-j}$. Consequently, $a_j b_j = a_j(a_{f^{-1}(j)} + 1) \geq a_j(a_{n+1-j} + 1) = a_j(3 - a_j) > 2$, which is a contradiction.

So for all $i \in [n]$, we have $a_i \in \{0, 1, 2\}$. Thus, the first t components of \vec{a} are 2, the last t components are 0, and the middle $n-2t$ components are 1, where $0 \leq t \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ (when n is even, there may be no 1 in the middle).

Thus, for all $1 \leq j \leq t$, we have $2(a_{f^{-1}(j)} + 1) = a_j b_j \leq 2$, so $a_{f^{-1}(j)} = 0$. Hence, for all $1 \leq j \leq t$, $f^{-1}(j) \geq n-t+1$.

Thus, for all $t+1 \leq j \leq n-t$, we have $a_{f^{-1}(j)} + 1 = a_j b_j \leq 2$, so $a_{f^{-1}(j)} \leq 1$. Hence, for all $t+1 \leq j \leq n-t$, $f^{-1}(j) \geq t+1$.

Since f is a bijection, and for all $1 \leq j \leq t$, $f^{-1}(j) \geq n-t+1$, it follows that for all $t+1 \leq j \leq n-t$, $t+1 \leq f^{-1}(j) \leq n-t$.

Because f is a bijection, for all $j \geq n-t+1$, $f^{-1}(j) \leq t$. Thus, for all $1 \leq j \leq t$, $f(j) \geq n-t+1$; for all $t+1 \leq j \leq n-t$, $t+1 \leq f(j) \leq n-t$; and for all $n-t+1 \leq j \leq n$, $1 \leq f(j) \leq t$. Verification shows that both \vec{a} and f satisfy the conditions in this case.

Therefore, all vectors \vec{a} satisfying the conditions are n -dimensional vectors where the first t components are 2, the last t components are 0, the middle $n-2t$ components are 1, and $0 \leq t \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ (when n is even, there may be no 1 in the middle).

Based on this, all bijections f satisfying the conditions are those that satisfy

$$\begin{cases} n-t+1 \leq f(j) \leq n & \text{for all } 1 \leq j \leq t, \\ t+1 \leq f(j) \leq n-t & \text{for all } t+1 \leq j \leq n-t, \\ 1 \leq f(j) \leq t & \text{for all } n-t+1 \leq j \leq n \end{cases}$$

from $[n]$ to $[n]$. (When n is even and $t = \frac{n}{2}$, there is no middle condition.)

5 The relationship between Problem 1 and Problem 2

Now that Conclusion 2 is known, we can prove Conclusion 1.

Under the hypotheses of the Conclusion 2, suppose there exists a sequence $\{b_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq n}$ such that for all $1 \leq i \leq n$, $a_i b_i < 2$. Then, for all $1 \leq i \leq n$, $a_i b_i \leq 2$. Without loss of generality, assume $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq \dots \geq a_n$. Then, by the conclusion 2, there exists $i \in [n]$ such that $a_i b_i = 2$. which is a contradiction. Hence, the Conclusion 1 is proved.

6 Another proof of Conclusion 1

First, we prove a lemma: If G is a finite directed graph (allowing loops) where each vertex has an out-degree and an in-degree of 1, then G can be decomposed into a disjoint union of finitely many directed cycles.

Using mathematical induction on $|G|$, the conclusion is correct when $|G|=2$.

Suppose the statement holds when $|G| \leq m-1$. For $|G| = m$, we start from any vertex A_1 in G . In the directed graph, let A_1 point to A_2 , A_2 point to A_3 , and so on. Let k be the smallest positive integer such that $A_k \in \{A_1, A_2, \dots, A_{k-1}\}$. Since $|G|$ is finite, k must exist.

Suppose $A_k = A_p$, where $1 \leq p \leq k-1$. If $p \neq 1$, then by the uniqueness of the out-degree and in-degree of each vertex, we have $A_{k-1} = A_{p-1}$, which contradicts the minimality of k . Thus, $A_k = A_1$.

In this way, $A_1 \rightarrow A_2 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow A_{k-1} \rightarrow A_k (= A_1)$ forms a directed cycle. Remove the edges of this cycle and the vertices in the cycle; the remaining sub-graph still satisfies the conditions. By the inductive hypothesis, the proof is completed.

Returning to the original problem, we construct a directed graph G with vertices $\{1, 2, \dots, n\}$.

By the problem's conditions, for each integer i with $1 \leq i \leq n$, there exists an index j such that $b_i = a_j + 1$, and each index j corresponds to a unique index $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. For such i and j , we draw a directed edge from i to j in G .

In this way, due to the uniqueness of the correspondence between i and j , each vertex in G has an out-degree and an in-degree of exactly 1. By the lemma, G can be decomposed into a disjoint union of some directed cycles.

Since the average of a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n is at least 1, by the property of averages, there must exist a cycle such that: if we let the set of all vertices in the cycle form an index set $I = \{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_t\}$ (where $i_1 \rightarrow i_2 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow i_t \rightarrow i_{t+1} = i_1$ is a cycle, and $i_{t+1} = i_1$), then the average of a_i for $i \in I$ is at least 1. We prove that there exists $i \in \{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_t\}$ such that $a_i b_i \geq 2$.

For $1 \leq j \leq t$, let $a_{i_j} = c_j$. To prove that there exists j such that $a_{i_j} b_{i_j} \geq 2$, it suffices to show that there exists j such that $a_{i_j}(a_{i_{j+1}} + 1) \geq 2$. That is, there exists $1 \leq j \leq t$ such that $c_j(c_{j+1} + 1) \geq 2$.

By the condition, $c_1 + c_2 + \cdots + c_t \geq t$. Without loss of generality, assume $c_1 + c_2 + \cdots + c_t = t$; otherwise, we can decrease some c_i to make $c_1 + c_2 + \cdots + c_t = t$.

Let j be such that $c_1 + c_2 + \cdots + c_{j-1} - (j - 1)$ is minimized (The indices are interpreted modulo n). We aim to prove $c_j(c_{j+1} + 1) \geq 2$. First, we show that $c_j \geq 1$ and $c_j + c_{j+1} \geq 2$. In fact, if this were not the case, replacing j with $j + 1$ or $j + 2$ would make $c_1 + c_2 + \cdots + c_{j-1} - (j - 1)$ smaller, which is a contradiction.

Now, $c_j \geq 1$ and $c_j + c_{j+1} \geq 2$. If $c_j \geq 2$, then $c_j(c_{j+1} + 1) \geq 2 \cdot 1 = 2$, which holds. Otherwise, $1 \leq c_j \leq 2$. We have

$$c_j(c_{j+1} + 1) \geq c_j(2 - c_j + 1) = c_j(3 - c_j) \geq 1 \cdot 2 = 2$$

which also holds. Thus, the proposition is proved.